

EMPOWERING STUDENTS THROUGH MENTAL HEALTH EDUCATION IN FAMILY-SCHOOL CO-EDUCATION

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Abstract

In the process of students' psychological development, addressing their inner contradictions and conflicts is crucial to prevent mental health problems. This article focuses on the importance of mental health education, utilizing psychological theories and educational methods tailored to students' growth stages. By nurturing psychological resilience and emotional well-being, this approach aims to eliminate negative psychological experiences, fostering a holistic development that harmonizes both physical and psychological aspects.

The family-school co-education model, which involves a collaborative effort between schools and parents in guiding children's growth, plays a pivotal role in this context. It not only influences students' learning but also has a significant impact on their mental health. To integrate mental health education effectively within the family-school co-education framework, teachers must employ scientific teaching methods to enhance students' psychological resilience. This approach results in more well-rounded development and improved educational outcomes.

1. Introduction

With the growth of teenagers, students' psychology gradually develops from childish to mature. In the process of mental state change, students' inner contradictions and conflicts cannot be guided in time, which will form mental health problems, and some even escalate to mental diseases, which will have a serious impact on students' study and life. Mental health education is the use of relevant theories and educational methods of psychology, combined with the psychological characteristics of students in different growth stages, to cultivate students' psychological quality, improve students' psychological adjustment ability, cultivate students' healthy psychological quality,

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eliminate the negative psychological emotions formed in the growth process, and promote the harmonious development of students' physiology and psychology.

The family-school co-education is a new education model, which means that schools and parents share the responsibility for children's growth, and it is an education system composed of school and family education [1]. Not only will it have an impact on pupils' learning, but it will also affect their mental health. Mental health has become an important part of modern education. By developing scientific education methods, teachers can strengthen students' psychological quality and enable them to get all-round development. Under the vision of family-school co-education, it carrying out mental health education in primary school can promote the continuous enhancement of students' psychological quality and improve the educational effect under the accurate and reasonable program.

2. The significance of family-school coordination in mental health education for students

In the process of growing up, students' cognition and psychology are a process that tends to mature gradually, and their growth can't be separated from family education and school education. At this stage, with many families attaching importance to mental health education, schools have put mental health education on the agenda and officially included in the goal of talent training. The family-school co-education can make management means more abundant, and constantly innovate in educational methods. At the same time, the school also guides parents' education methods, so that parents can master a more scientific model to get along with their children, and then guide their children, more scientific, and promote the psychological development of students to maintain a healthy state [2]. In the important factors affecting students' mental health, the family occupies an important part, the school should strengthen cooperation with the family to ensure that the development of students' mental health has enough psychological dreg mechanism, so that children feel the warmth from the family in the process of growing up, in the emergence of mental health problems, in order to get rehabilitation, to promote the mental health of students.

2.1 Co-education between schools is helpful to carry out comprehensive mental health education

Since the development of quality education in China, all sectors of society pay more and more attention to students' mental health problems, and education departments and related teaching institutions are also actively carrying out students' mental health education activities. From the current situation of the development of students' mental health education, the methods adopted basically include the organization of special activities, the establishment of mental health counseling stations, and the penetration of mental health knowledge in various disciplines, etc [3]. Although unprecedented results have been achieved, it is far from being able to fundamentally solve the needs of students' mental health development. On the one hand, the school mental health education manpower and material resources are limited, psychological education is difficult to go deep; On the other hand, school education is only a part of students' education, and in the absence of family education, the effect of mental health education is difficult to play. Carrying out home-school co-parenting will help mental health education cover the whole process of students' growth, and families and schools can complement each other to meet students' mental health needs to the greatest extent.

2.2 The family-school co-education helps to make up for the shortage of educational resources

The development of economic construction has a great impact on the development of regional education in China. In some economically developed provinces and regions, the development of education is also relatively fast, while in some economically backward regions, there are many deficiencies in both educational hardware facilities and teaching resources. To improve the quality of mental health education in schools, it is necessary to constantly improve theory and practice. However, students' mental health education has become a top priority. As an important part of students' education, family education needs to give play to its own special advantages, actively participate in students' mental health counseling, establish cooperative relations with schools, and provide corresponding support for schools to carry out mental health counseling, so as to achieve good educational results.

2.3 The family-school co-education helps to give full play to the function of family education

Mental health education is not simply knowledge imparting and skills training, but involves the improvement of internal factors such as thinking mode, self-cognition and psychological emotions, which are gradually formed based on students' living and learning environment. It is far from enough to rely solely on the school to carry out mental health education, and the school environment and family environment need to have a joint impact, so as to solve the root cause of students' mental health problems. Therefore, the characteristics of mental health education give family education special education function, only through the family-school co-education, it can make mental health education more perfect.

3. Problems existing in promoting students' mental health growth through family-school co-education

3.1 The quality of co-education activities needs to be improved

In recent years, education departments and schools in many regions of China have organized parent-child activities and themed class meetings to attract parents' participation in student education and promote interaction and communication between parents and students, so as to improve students' mental health [4]. However, from the actual effect, the family-school relationship established in this way is only limited to the surface level, and parents are only participants in the activity, and have not fully played their educational functions. In addition, through this kind of widely participating activity, it has a strong universality, but it can't carry out effective psychological counseling for students, and the role of parents in the process of participation is also restricted.

3.2 The organization mode of school co-education activities is single

Judging from the current situation of the organization of students' psychological education activities in China, it is still limited to the state of school and society as the organizers and the participation of students' parents, and the lack of effective interaction among school, society and family. Therefore, the current co-education mode of mental health education in China is still in the embryonic stage, and it is still centered on school education, and parents and society are centered around school education. To achieve good effect of mental health education, deeper cooperation is needed. Parents need to be deeply involved in the school's mental health education process, in various mental health education activities, is no longer a simple participant, but their children's mentors. Only in this way can parents really play a role in mental health education.

3.3 The school's guidance on family-school co-education is not perfect

Family education is an important part of all students' education and has a significant impact on students' mental health. However, in the long-term development of China's education, family education is often weakened,

especially in the social development environment centered on economic construction in recent years, some family education is not perfect, and even brings many negative effects to students. According to data released by the Ministry of Civil Affairs, the divorce rate in China will exceed 43.53 percent in 2022. In a sample survey conducted by the All-China Women's Federation, domestic violence accounted for 16 percent of cases. These data show that the current family education environment in China needs to be further improved, and parents need to be aware of the impact of family environment on students' mental health problems.

Students' mental health problems mostly come from the disharmonious family environment and atmosphere. Parents should play a leading role in students' mental health education. But in the actual education, parents often lack the necessary psychological counseling knowledge and counseling means, which leads to the lack of family psychological counseling education. However, in the mental health education of students, the school often ignores the improvement of parents' mental health counseling ability and lacks counseling for students' parents.

3.4 Lack of publicity for the family-school co-education

The factors that restrict the educational effect of family-school co-education in the process of students' mental health education mainly come from the lack of parents' cognition of students' mental health status and the lack of understanding of relevant knowledge and means of psychological education. Quality education and mental health education started late in China, and parents of students have not paid enough attention to students' mental health problems. Especially in the long-term exam-oriented education environment, students' parents pay more attention to students' academic performance and school ranking, ignoring students' mental health problems. At present, there are still many shortcomings in the promotion of students' mental health education. Although relevant education departments attach great importance to students' mental health problems, and some teaching institutions are constantly strengthening mental health counseling, there is still much room for improvement in social media and school publicity. Lack of family education assistance and support, school education is often difficult to do alone.

3.5 Lack of teachers for mental health education

Many school teachers in China have undergone formal professional training and have certain professional knowledge of psychology [5]. However, in practice, faced with a large number of students and various causes and manifestations of students' mental health conditions, it is difficult to implement mental health education in a targeted way, which further affects the effect of students' mental health counseling. In addition, teachers should not only bear the pressure of curriculum teaching, strive to improve the quality of teaching, but also carry out psychological counseling for students' mental health problems, which has obviously exceeded the teacher's energy load. In addition, although many teachers have some basic psychological knowledge, but the lack of counseling practice experience, professional psychological testing and psychological counseling skills are limited, which also affects the effect of students' mental health education.

3.6 The subject of collaborative education is not clear

First of all, the main body of family-school collaborative education is mainly schools and parents, at this stage, there are some parents in the face of children's education problems, think that the school bears the main responsibility, they are only responsible for life, and even some parents believe that mental health education needs to be fully undertaken by the school. These parents have a weak awareness of mental health education, and believe

that communication with the school is limited to the child's learning, because the level of their children's academic performance is the barometer of the quality of school education, ignoring their children's mental health. Secondly, in the family-school cooperation, the school, as the main body of student management, has a strong arbitrariness when penetrating mental health education, and has not formulated a perfect mental health education plan, which is merely a formality and plays a substantive role.

The contents of family-school cooperative education include family education and student education. In the healthy growth of students, family education plays a very important role, schools need to teach parents scientific education methods, including mental health education knowledge, need to carry out a series of training. Because some students have weak knowledge transfer ability and poor ability to apply school knowledge in life, it is easy to cause the problem of disconnection between parents and school education.

4. Strategies of family-school co-education to promote students' mental health growth

The problem of students' mental health is not only related to their personal healthy growth and development, but also related to the development and progress of Chinese society. Students' mental health problems can't be separated from the impact of the environment. The environment that students face in their growth mainly comes from three aspects: family environment, school environment and social environment. Therefore, to promote family-school co-education and promote students' mental health growth, it is necessary to form a tripartite force.

4.1 Social level

First of all, to promote students' mental health growth through the family-school co-education, the education department needs to strengthen the implementation and promotion, and strengthen the publicity of family-school co-education psychological education. The education department needs to organize experts and scholars with professional knowledge and experience in mental health education to investigate the mental health of students in the local area, sum up the problems existing in the current mental health of students, and work out solutions in line with the actual local situation; Education departments should form publicity forces with social media to improve the public's attention to students' mental health problems, increase the public's mental health education knowledge to achieve family-school co-education, and lay the foundation for carrying out mental health education.

Secondly, to promote students' mental health growth through the family-school co-education, education departments need to strengthen the supervision of the construction of family-school co-education organizations at all levels. Many schools have established administrative parent committee, but in the actual education work, play the role and achieve the effect is not ideal, the reason is the lack of pertinence, the content is too broad. Therefore, it is necessary to combine the incentives of students' mental health problems and establish professional parent committees by classification and stratification, so as to organize mental health education activities in a targeted manner, ensure that mental health education means are consistent with students' mental health needs, and achieve good educational results.

Finally, it carrying out family-school co-education for students' mental health education is extensive and universal, and each education and teaching institution will accumulate some good experience and educational methods in the specific implementation process. The education departments should actively organize family-school co-education work exchange activities and invite experts with professional mental health education to

provide guidance and training, advising on the work of the parent committee. This can not only improve the professional level of mental health education, but also help expand the social influence of family-school co-education to promote students' mental health education.

4.2 School level

First of all, to promote students' mental health growth through the family-school co-education, schools need to carry out family-school co-education related activities. At present, some schools set up themed class meetings and parent-child travel, parent-child entertainment and other activities, have played a good educational effect, enhance the communication between students and parents, and create opportunities for parent-child interaction. The school can learn from the experience of other schools in organizing activities, combined with the actual situation of the school's education work, and carry out family-school co-education activities with the characteristics of the school. For example, organize festival activities, holiday travel activities, etc., enhance the emotional communication between parents and students, use family interaction and emotional care to give a positive impact on students' mental health problems, and promote the development of students' mental health; Secondly, we can organize the establishment of mental health expert lectures, mental health counseling skills training, etc., to create opportunities for students' parents to improve their own mental health counseling skills.

Secondly, to promote students' mental health growth through the family-school co-education, schools need to refine mental health education work, conduct in-depth exchanges with students' parents, understand the root causes of students' mental health problems, and analyze the impact of the current environment on students' mental state. Through the cooperation of school and family, improve students' living and learning environment, so as to achieve better mental health counseling effect. For example, some adolescent students are in the stage of physical and psychological changes, at this time, parents are precisely in the menopause stage, it is easy to produce friction and emotional collision between parents and children, students often show emotional instability, irritability, lack of trust in the family environment and other characteristics. Through the family-school co-education, we can understand the root causes of students' psychological problems, so that we can take targeted guidance, improve the understanding between parents and children, use parent-child activities, so that parents feel each other's love, and deepen parent-child feelings at the same time, promote students' mental health growth.

Finally, in the mental health education of students, teachers should constantly improve themselves and improve their mental health counseling skills. Teachers often have a high status in the minds of students and are the model of students' learning. Many students attach more importance to the guidance and suggestions of teachers. Therefore, teachers need to reflect their own advantages in education in family-school co-education, so as to realize the complementary effect of family education and school education. The improvement of teachers' psychological guidance skills will help to bring this advantage into play.

4.3 Family level

First of all, parents should fully understand the practical significance of the family-school co-education, and be clear about the responsibilities and obligations that parents need to assume in the growth process of students. Parents need to actively integrate into family-school education, understand the psychological state of students through cooperation with the school, improve the level of family education through their own learning and efforts,

and create a good growth environment for students. It provide a harmonious living atmosphere, and school similarities and differences to solve students' mental health problems, promote the healthy growth of students. Secondly, according to the concept of family-school co-education, mental health education should be carried out from a comprehensive and normative perspective to ensure the full implementation of the cooperation mechanism. To carry out family-school cooperation activities, schools need to know about students' families in advance. It is necessary to regularly explore the common mental health problems of primary school students, but also to understand the opinions of parents in mental health education. In the formulation of cooperation content, the frequency of cooperation and docking personnel in the cooperation process should be clearly stipulated, and communication and exchange should be carried out [6]. The cooperation results can be pre-evaluated in advance, the difficulty of the target can be predicted, and whether the cooperation can achieve the goal, and the cooperation plan should be formulated.

Finally, the school extends the development of collaborative support mechanisms, but also in-depth understanding of each student's family life, choose a fixed time to understand the situation, guide parents to master the correct education methods, so that parents in the implementation of family education is more appropriate, which is an important link to ensure the implementation of mental health education. It is necessary to let parents and teachers contact each other frequently, implement mental health education, and let students know that the hard work of teachers and parents is for their healthy growth, so that students have the motivation to move forward in their hearts. In addition, for some parents who are far away from the school, the school can learn about the learning and psychological status of these students through network live classes or Wechat group building, and teach parents more advanced teaching methods to ensure that families who are remote from the school can also obtain high-quality education resources.

5. Conclusion

Family education and school education play an important role in the growth of students, but in real life, both of them are restricted by their own conditions, it can't fully play the educational effect. Through family-school co-education, schools and families unite to form educational forces, achieve complementary resources and advantages, and jointly create a good living and learning environment for students, in order to promote the healthy psychological growth of students.

References

- Li C H, Xu W N, Kang J. The Theoretical Foundation and Strategic Innovation of Home-school Co-education in Primary and Secondary Schools in the New Period [J]. *Modern Education Management*, 2019, (11): 12-17.
- Zhou R, Zou Y H. Exploration on Creating Students' Mental Health Education Model through Home-School Co-Education [J]. *Journal of Dalian Education University*, 2019, 35(1): 71-73.

Shen Z Y, Zhao X J. Thoughts and Probes into Mental Health Education for Students in High Schools under the Background of Co-education between Home and School [J]. Journal of the College of Northwest Adult Education, 2022, (5): 93-97.

Bian Y F, Zhang X Y. How to Do Well in Family Education Guidance under the Pattern of “Easing the Burden of Excessive Homework and Off-campus Tutoring for Students Undergoing Compulsory Education” [J]. China Educational Technology, 2022, (5): 8-12+34.

Kang L Y. Provide precise guidance for children on home school co-education [J]. People's Education, 2019, (22): 13-16.

Wang Y M. The Education instead of Control: A Probe into Family-School Education in the Internet Environment [J]. Theory and Practice of Education, 2018, 38(26): 23-25.